

to separate the categories of users on it in its 2014 report.

Although infamously undesirable for the average moral person, the dark web provides perfect anonymity when exploring the Internet. Anonymity is followed by actions that are prohibited in certain parts of the world, such as drug industries, weapon markets, credit fraud, identity theft, sensitive information leaks, and so on.

In his study titled "Old wine in new bottles?" Peter Grabosky describes how virtual crime is remarkably similar to real-world physical crime, with the main difference being the medium in which both are done.¹ He goes on to demonstrate how virtual criminality and terrestrial criminality are equivalent, omitting the terms for implementing technology.

The emergence of the dark web has made criminal behavior easier. DDoS assaults that need the participation of several collaborators are now as simple as renting a botnet that can implement a DDoS as a Service (DDoSaaS) on a specific network. Ransomware that formerly required hacking knowledge to install is now simply buyable and even deployable on the dark web.²

The dark web encourages youthful hackers to participate by providing opportunities to make money. As a result, the darknet has unintentionally become a recruiting tool for those looking to make a life from it. As a result, the existence of the dark web has permitted and even encouraged the interaction of harmful people.

¹ P. Grabosky, "Virtual Criminality: Old Wine in New Bottles?," in Social & Legal Studies 10: 243–49, 2001. https://openresearch-repository.anu.edu.au/bitstream/1885/26506/2/01_Grabosky_Digital_Crime_in_the_2003.pdf

² T. L., "Dark Hatred: Antisemitism on the Dark Web," in Journal of Contemporary Antisemitism, 2, 25-42., 2019. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338350246_Dark_Hatred_Antisemitism_on_the_Dark_Web

Furthermore, some private firms have employed dark web intruders.³

Because of the decades-long Cold War between power nations, it has been stated that each nation should begin preparing for a digital war that would be more powerful than a physical battle at this time. The influence of digital entities on Critical Infrastructure (CI) and Industrial Control Systems (ICS) is thought to be the source of the aforementioned rationale.⁴ According to some study, the dark web is "a planet of cybercrime", referring to the diversity and proliferation of criminality on it. For an inquisitive surface internet user, the risk of being able to reach that world of criminality by taking a few easy steps is not very secure. Despite the simple directions, the accessible literature on the surface web about how to reach the dark web appears to warn the user about its hazards.

Furthermore, because of the murky image earned by certain types of hacktivist organizations on the dark web as a result of their help for terrorism prevention, activities such as dark web journalism and anonymous speech forums are more likely to be illegal. This section continues to explore some of the most popular dark web crimes.

The dark web has a wide range of implications on the web, including the suppression of illicit material and the promotion of criminal activity. According to

³ T. Lev, "Dark and Deep Webs-Liberty or Abuse," in International Journal of Cyber Warfare and Terrorism, 9, 1-14., 2019. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333711045_Dark_and_Deep_Webs-Liberty_or_Abuse>

⁴ B. R. Alkhatib B, "Mining the Dark Web: A novel approach for placing a Dark Website under investigation," in International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science, 11(10), 1-13., 2019., <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336262830_Mining_the_Dark_Web_A_Novel_Approach_for_Placing_a_Dark_Website_under_Investigation>

Beshiri and Susuri's⁵ research, unlawful content is utilized at a rate of 57% on the dark web. Other notable crimes committed on the dark web include illicit drug trafficking, terrorist communication, weapon trafficking, forged money exchanges, child pornographic content, stolen financial data selling, and unlawful conversation. According to forensic investigators, one of the most severe issues is the anonymous user's privacy.⁶ Furthermore, TOR, Freenet, I2P, and JobDonvm are some of the most popular unnamed programs used in conjunction with the dark web for access.

Apart from trading and purchasing illicit goods and services, racial hate organizations thrive on the uncontrolled deep and dark webs. If hate speech and provocation are banned in their native countries, neo-Nazi bloggers, activists, or organized groups seek refuge in the dark web. The latest Charlottesville rallies are a well-known example. The rallies are called "Unit the Right," but they are organized by a website called the Daily Stormer. Heather Heyer, 32, was killed in August 2017 when a white supremacist drove into a protest opposing the alt-right 'Unit the Right'.⁷ Following the event, Google and GoDaddy refused to host the neo-Nazi website, and the Daily Stormer sought refuge on the dark web. The site administrators began hosting a site on the dark web¹⁶. When they discovered a means to return to the ordinary surface web a few months later, they made a declaration saying that if their site is taken down, fans should go to their dark web

⁵ A. S. Arbër S Beshiri, "Dark Web and Its Impact in Online," in Journal of Computer and Communications, 7, 30-43., Kosovo, 2019., <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331867659_Dark_Web_and_Its_Impact_in_Online_Anonymity_and_Privacy_A_Critical_Analysis_and_Review>

⁶ C. M, "A public policy perspective of the Dark Web," in Journal of Cyber Policy. 2. 1-13, 2017., <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362267622_The_Dark_Web_-_A_Review>

⁷ The Daily Stormer's new dark web site: <<https://dstormer6em3i4km.onion.link>>

site.

Individuals or well-structured organizations can commit cybercrime or terrorism on the dark web. Cybercrime is becoming more accessible to anybody who wants to engage in low-risk illegal activities while yet making a difference (for example, executing DDoS assaults on websites is as simple as contracting a botnet that provides DDoS-as-a-Service).⁸ These services enable attackers to target 'low hanging fruit' (targets with insufficient security safeguards or instruction). Tor's secret services can help in complex assaults that include maintaining command-and-control (C2) lines between attackers and victims. Tor's anonymity (and difficulties in shutting down) is suitable for C2 servers, and it is one of the most popular hidden services accessible.⁹

On the Dark Web, any form of crime involving clandestine transactions, whether it includes narcotics, money, or even human people, can be perpetrated. The darkest areas of the internet serve as a platform for a wide range of crimes. Here are some examples of crimes committed on the Dark Web:

Murder for Hire: The website Besa Mafia (and others like it) are contract killing marketplaces.

Extortion/Blackmail: One scam involves threats of publishing sensitive information or compromising images until the victim pays a predetermined sum of bitcoin.

Illegal Drug Sales: AlphaBay was the most popular Dark Web bazaar for

⁸ Crawley, A. 2016. "Hiring Hackers," Network Security (2016:9), pp. 13-15.,

⁹ Biryukov, A., Pustogarov, I., Thill, F., and Weinmann, R.-P. 2014. "Content and Popularity Analysis of Tor Hidden Services," Distributed Computing Systems Workshops (ICDCSW), 2014 IEEE 34th International Conference on: IEEE, pp. 188-193.

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which are frequently used for illegal activities such as drug trafficking, money laundering, and cybercrime. It serves as a sharp reminder that the dark web is becoming a more appealing venue for criminals to carry out their operations, and that more needs to be done to tackle this rising problem.

60% of darknet sellers sell hacked bank credentials. This figure serves as a sharp reminder of the ubiquity of financial credential theft on the darknet, emphasizing the importance of enhanced attention in securing one's financial details. It serves as a warning to people who are ignorant of the dangers lying in the dark web, emphasizing the need of taking the required precautions to avoid being a victim of such crimes.

More over a third (37%) of dark web purchases lead to more illegal conduct. This figure serves as a striking reminder of the pervasiveness of illicit activities on the dark web. It emphasizes the fact that a considerable part of dark web purchases are used to assist additional illegal behavior, making it a dangerous and possibly lucrative platform for criminals. This figure serves as a warning that the dark web is not a secure environment in which to do business and should be handled with care.

96% of thieves use the encrypted chat software Telegram to conduct their operations. This figure serves as a striking reminder of the pervasiveness of cybercrime and the extent to which criminals will go to stay unknown. It emphasizes the significance of increasing security measures to guard against the threat of cybercrime, as well as remaining up to speed on the most recent dark web crime data.

Between 2017 and 2019, the number of child maltreatment sites on the dark

web increased by 21%. This figure serves as a startling reminder of how quickly child exploitation websites are flourishing on the dark web. It is intended to serve as a wake-up call to law enforcement and other stakeholders to take immediate action to combat this horrible crime.

In 2017, the projected global income earned from medicine sales on the dark web was \$600 million. This number serves as a harsh reminder of the dark web's enormous financial power. It emphasizes the fact that the dark web is a profitable market for criminal operations, with drug sales playing a significant role in its development. It also serves as a reminder that the dark web is a hazardous area where criminal activity may have major financial consequences.

After a cyber-attack event in 2020, 867,560 healthcare records were leaked on the dark web. This figure serves as a harsh reminder of the possible ramifications of a cyber-attack disaster. It emphasizes the dangers of the dark web, where criminals may access and exploit sensitive information, and that healthcare data are especially vulnerable to such attacks. It is a sobering reminder that enterprises must take precautions to protect their data and maintain the security of their systems.

In 2018, there were over 1,000 illicit markets on the dark web. This figure serves as a striking reminder of the pervasiveness of illegal marketplaces on the dark web. It serves as a reminder that the dark web is a hub of illicit activity, with an expanding number of unlawful marketplaces. It serves as a sobering reminder that the dark web is a hazardous place, and that criminals use its anonymity to carry out their nefarious operations.

In 2019, 9 out of every 10 dark web search results were for illicit activity. This figure serves as a striking reminder of the pervasiveness of criminal activity

associated with some type of illicit activity. The amount of dark web markets increased by 44% in 2019, with over 8,000 separate stores retailing over 45,000 product listings tied to criminality. In addition, 60% of merchants sell stolen bank credentials, while 37% of transactions result in additional criminal activity, such as phishing (59%). Drug sales on the dark web produced an estimated \$600 million in worldwide income in 2017, while firearms-related listings climbed by 65% between 2013 and 2019. Furthermore, the number of kidnapping and victimization webpages has increased by 21%, the delivery of ransom has increased by 200%, \$76 billion in Bitcoins were laundered in 2020, and the average cost per credit card record is \$25. Criminals continue to develop new ways to exploit weaknesses online, aided by the private nature provided by the dark web, thus making it harder for law enforcement authorities to hunt down perpetrators of these crimes.¹²

To sum up, organizations or companies do not publicly sponsor or resource hackers. As a result, they must seek financial gain from the scams and cybercrimes they commit. As a result, they place a premium on the method, timing, and location of cybercrime in the digital battlefield. In contrast to the aggressive tendency of cyber criminals, internet users, whether on the dark and surface webs, must be defensively alert in order to protect themselves against cybercrime.¹³

Regardless of the platform used, cybercriminals constantly rely on the Internet to carry out their nefarious operations. For example, traditional crimes such as sex trafficking or drug distribution through the Internet always rely on a

¹² GITNUXBLOG “The Most Surprising Dark Web Crime Statistics And Trends in 2023”, <<https://blog.gitnux.com/dark-web-crime-statistics/>>

¹³ C. Easttom, "Conducting investigations on the Dark Web," in *Journal of Information Warfare*, 17(4), 26-37., 2018., <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/e26783819>>

network to carry out the financial transactions. Additionally, while committing a technology cybercrime, such as intellectual property theft, identity theft, or credit card fraud, the usage of a digital subdomain is always present.

Following from previous war methods, deterrence and dissuasion are usually referred to be successful winning strategies. However, using both strategies to combat cybercrime is claimed to be useless. This is due to the fact that virtual environments do not function in the same manner as actual environments. Despite possible criticism, hacktivist organizations have been working alongside legislative agencies throughout the world to reduce and remove terrorism-related activity from the dark web. These activities sparked a movement on the dark web.

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